

Towards defining “Responsible Living Labs” in the era of digital transformation and AI

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Abstract

This research-in-progress article explores how living labs (LLs) as a facilitator of digital transformation (DT) activities should be in line with responsible research and innovation (RRI) principles. This alignment gains special prominence when DT processes leverage AI-driven innovations and have a young citizen demographic as the focus. In so doing, we propose the new concept called "Responsible Living Labs" (RLL) as an overarching framework for LL researchers and practitioners to ensure transparency, stakeholder engagement, ethical considerations, and sustainability in all stages of LL activities and actions. The research methodology involves conducting a systematic literature review and organizing a workshop at Open Living Lab Days 2023 conference within the context of Interreg Baltic Sea Region project UrbanTestbeds.JR (#S004). This will be done to explore the potential of AI in fostering RRI in LL activities, as well as ethical challenges and other RRI related concerns that LLs are facing when young citizen are engaged. The study will contribute to the body of knowledge by bridging the gap in research on how LL activities can be more responsible and ethical while benefiting from advanced technologies such as AI.

Key words

Living Lab, Responsible Research and Innovation, Young citizen engagement, Artificial Intelligence, Digital Transformation, Ethics

Introduction

Currently, digital transformation (DT) is changing the dynamics of society and shaping how we live and work (Agarwal, 2020). DT can be understood as the “changes that digital technology causes or influences in all aspects of human life” (Stolterman & Fors, 2004, p. 689). DT greatly relies on the use of advanced digital technologies, in which many of them are driven by artificial intelligence (AI) (Holmström, 2022). AI is a particularly powerful enabler of DT since it has the ability to learn from data, identify patterns, and make predictions, all without human intervention (Verhoef et al., 2021). As AI becomes more intertwined into our daily lives, it's vital to ensure that its development and use is in line with ethical principles and societal values, the so-called Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) (Owen et al., 2012). RRI is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products (in order to allow a proper embedding of scientific and technological advances in our society) (Bajmócy & Pataki, 2019).

There are various approaches that researchers and practitioners use to ensure that DT activities are in line with RRI principles, such as open science, citizen science, Living Lab (LL), and so forth. This research is focused on DT activities and actions which are supported and facilitated by a living lab as the overall approach (Bagalkot, 2009; Schaffers et al., 2009; Schuurman, 2015), with a particular emphasis on young citizen engagement. LLs have been introduced and proposed as an inclusive and sustainable approach involving various stakeholders, focusing on individuals in their role as citizens, inhabitants, end-users etc., are engaged throughout the DT process in their real-life setting (Bergvall-Kåreborn et al., 2009; Ståhlbröst, 2008). Accordingly, LLs can be seen as an approach for innovation development processes, as they allow one to simultaneously focus on individuals, technologies, tasks and structures, and the interactions between different stakeholders (Schaffers et al., 2009).

Despite this, the implementation of DT in LL activities also poses significant ethical and social challenges (Habibipour et al., 2018), particularly when it comes to AI driven innovations with and for young citizens, and there is a dearth of research on how LL activities should be more responsible and ethical, while benefiting from advanced technologies such as AI throughout DT processes (Ruffolo, 2022; Saurabh et al., 2021). Accordingly, this research-in-progress aims at exploring how our LL activities and actions should be in line with RRI, when it comes to AI driven DT processes with a

particular emphasis on young citizen engagement. To achieve the aim of this study, we will introduce the term “Responsible Living Lab” (RLL) as an overarching framework for LL researchers and practitioners. The proposed framework emphasizes the need for transparency, stakeholder engagement, ethical considerations, and sustainability in all stages of LL activities and actions and identifies key principles and best practices for implementing RLLs.

Research Methodology

To address the aim of this research-in-progress, we have started conducting a systematic literature review, which will be complemented by the results of a workshop on the AI’s role in enabling RRL, opportunities for co-creation, innovation, and address challenges and consequences of DT for human and society as a whole. The workshop will be done in the context of Interreg Baltic Sea Region project UrbanTestbeds.JR (#S004) and is planned to be held at the Open Living Lab Days 2023 conference. The workshop follows a reverse brainstorming approach that enables participants to discuss both problems and solutions.

UrbanTestbeds.JR aims to foster resilient communities through co-designed urban testbeds, emphasizing tangible sustainability experiences for young citizens. The project focuses on enhancing participatory capacity and inclusivity in addressing climate and sustainability challenges, incorporating AI-driven climate plan analysis and urban data storytelling.

When it comes to the systematic literature review, we started by following a concept-centric approach as outlined by Webster and Watson (2002). This approach contrasts with the author’s centric approach in which the readers are usually familiar with the main topic and there are already available studies that discussed the main topic in detail. We chose the concept-centric method as it allows us to systematically synthesize the literature and enables us to create a preliminary classification on the food analytics literature.

The process of conducting a literature review on LL research began by determining the primary journals and conferences in the field, namely, Technology Innovation Management Review, Sustainability, Frontier, and the Open Living Lab Days conference. These sources are considered to be the main generators of LL research within the community. We started going through the table of contents of each of these core journals and conferences and manually search for the relevant articles by reviewing the

title, abstract, and keywords of the articles. In addition to the core journals, we will expand our search for the articles in online databases (namely, Scopus, Web of Science, EBSCO, PubMed, MDPI, and Taylor & Francis), using the search terms for literature search. The keywords that are used for this systematic literature review are: Living Lab (LL), Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Citizen engagement and Digital transformation (DT). Any meaningful combinations of these keywords are included as a search term.

Finally, to identify further relevant studies, backward and forward citation analysis based on Webster and Watson's (2002) recommendation will be conducted. We employ this approach because the number of relevant findings in the preliminary step was too few to obtain reliable results. In this article, due to the emerging nature of RRL, we will also include the secondary resources (i.e., sources that analyze, interpret, or summarize primary literature), such as industrial and consultancy reports, project deliverables, press, and so on. However, only publications in English language will be considered in this review and no time limitation was set.

When it comes to the workshop, participants will be engaged in collaborative discussions and brainstorming activity to co-create the definition of RLL. Through co-creation activities and group discussions, LL researchers and practitioners will gain insights into the potential of AI in fostering responsible research and innovation (RRI) in LL activities, including young citizen engagement, co-creation, and innovation development in real-life settings. They will also discover the ethical considerations and challenges associated with AI in LL activities for and with young citizens, such as dehumanization of actions, responsibility, transparency, as well as imbalance in power distribution, and the digital divide. Our workshop aims to provide a milieu for contributors to share their knowledge, experiences, and perspectives, and collectively develop a deeper understanding of RLL with a particular focus on DT and AI.

Preliminary results

The increasing use of AI in DT in various domains raises ethical and social considerations, such as bias, accountability, transparency, dehumanization of actions, digital divide, and privacy issues (Kim et al., 2021; Nadoleanu et al., 2022; Saurabh et al., 2021). These challenges are particularly pertinent in the context of LL actions (Harbers & Overdiek, 2022), which are real-world settings for research and innovation that involve stakeholders in co-creation, experimentation, and evaluation processes. The unique features of LLs, such as the involvement of end-users and other

stakeholders in the innovation process, create both opportunities and challenges for the implementation of AI powered DT in all individual, organizational and the societal level (Frey et al., 2022; Harbers & Overdiek, 2022).

One example of an ethical challenge in LL activities is ensuring that the data to be used to train AI models is representative of the population (Ruffolo, 2022). For example, in a co-creation activity involving the development of a health app, if the data used to train the AI models is biased towards a certain population group, the resulting app may not be effective or safe for other population groups. Additionally, if the AI system used to make decisions in the app perpetuates societal biases, it may lead to unequal treatment or discrimination against certain groups (Nebeker et al., 2019).

Another example of an ethical challenge is ensuring that AI systems used in LL activities are transparent and accountable (Hasenauer et al., 2022). If the data driven decisions which are made using AI tools are not transparent enough, it might be challenging for stakeholders to assess whether the decisions are fair and unbiased. Moreover, it may be difficult to ensure that the decisions are in line with ethical and social considerations (Lepri et al., 2017).

While there are challenges associated with the use of AI DT process that follow LL approach, there are also significant opportunities to employ AI driven tools to foster DT in LLs. One way which AI can support RRLs is by enabling more inclusive and participatory decision-making processes (Lepri et al., 2017). By including large amounts of data (the so-called big data) from various stakeholders and individual users, AI can provide insights into the needs and preferences of different LL actors, which enhances the inclusion of various parties in the decisions (Bibri, 2019). For example, in a co-creation activity of developing a smart city solution, AI can be used as an enabler to analyze data on traffic patterns, energy consumption, public transport use, and help the city planners to better identify the needs and preferences of all stakeholders, including public and private sectors and citizens (Bibri, 2019).

Overall, these opportunities highlight the potential for AI to support RRI in LLs by enabling more inclusive, transparent, and efficient decision-making processes, and accelerating innovation cycles. However, it is important to ensure that these opportunities are realized in a responsible and ethical manner, taking into account the challenges and risks associated with the use of AI in LL activities.

Discussions and future steps

The next step in this research-in-progress will be to complete the literature review and synthesize the results with the workshop on defining a framework for RRL. In so doing, we will identify the key principles and best practices for defining and further implementing RLLs for young citizens. The proposed framework for RRL will emphasize transparency, stakeholder engagement, ethical considerations, and sustainability in all stages of LL activities and actions. Additionally, the researchers can also explore how this framework can be implemented in real-world LL activities and actions, particularly those that involve AI-driven solutions for DT processes.

One of the key benefits of using a Responsible Living Lab (RLL) approach is to ensure LL researchers and practitioner that their research is conducted in a way that is more aligned with RRI principles, which are becoming increasingly important in the development and use of advanced technologies such as AI (Frey et al., 2022; Nebeker et al., 2019). Another key benefit of using an RLL approach is that it can help LL practitioners to create more inclusive and sustainable innovation processes. RLLs prioritize early stakeholder engagement and inclusion (Habibipour et al., 2021), which means that they involve individuals in their role as citizens, inhabitants, end-users, etc., throughout the DT process in their real-life setting. This can help to ensure that the innovation process is more aligned with the needs and values of the stakeholders who will ultimately use the digital solutions (Habibipour et al., 2021). RLLs also focus on the interactions between different stakeholders, which can help to foster collaboration and co-creation. Finally, RLLs emphasize the need for sustainability in all stages of their activities and actions, which can help to ensure that the innovation process is more environmentally and socially responsible (Bajmócy & Pataki, 2019; Harbers & Overdiek, 2022).

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the European Commission in the context of Interreg Baltic Sea Region project UrbanTestbeds.JR (#S004), and Horizon Europe project SYN AIR-G (Grant Agreement No. 101057271), which is gratefully acknowledged.

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